

Hydrodynamic and mechanical behavior of multi-particle confined between two parallel plates

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Abstract

A coupled Computational Fluid Dynamics-Discrete Element Method (CFD-DEM) approach is used to investigate the hydrodynamic and mechanical behavior of multi-particles, which settle vertically and transport horizontally between two parallel plates. The particle-fluid interaction is two-way hydrodynamically and mechanically coupled, while inter-particle and particle-wall interactions are calculated based on the soft-sphere model. The Joint Roughness Coefficient (JRC) is used to represent the roughness of planar walls, and its effect on particle transport is quantitatively studied. When particles transport between two parallel smooth plates, the planar walls exert extra hydrodynamic retardation, which causes particle transport velocity to decrease with the decrease in the aperture between two plates. In contrast, when particles transport between two parallel rough plates, due to frequent interact between particles, the mechanical interaction-induced retardation starts to work and further decreases particle transport velocity. Particle longitudinal migration is frequent because of inter-particle interactions, which hinder its transverse transport and even cause particle agglomeration in a channel during horizontal transport. In addition, mechanical retardation is significantly dependent on particle transport regimes, and its effect gradually increases and changes to be dominant at high particle Reynold number regime.

Keywords: Particle-fluid flow; parallel plates; CFD-DEM; JRC; hydrodynamic and mechanical retardation

1. Introduction

Transport of fluid mixed with particles exists in a wide variety of natural and industrial processes. Typical examples include fluidization bed, sand transport in rivers and lakes, wastewater discharge, proppant transport during hydraulic fracturing, etc. [1-3]. During these two-phase flow processes, frequent momentum exchange between particles and fluids occurs. Two important mechanisms govern particle motion in a fluid: particle settlement and fluid drag. Flowing fluid exerts drag force on particles, changing particle transport

velocity, and this in turn affects fluid flow. The two-way particle-fluid coupling interaction causes a complex process of particle-fluid flow. In addition, particle motion is significantly dependent of inter-particle interaction. For dense phase transport of particles, particles frequently collide with each other, and this even can dominate their motion and significantly increase disturbance of flow field. When a particle-fluid mix flows in a finite channel, the interactions between particles and walls further cause the flow to be more complex. Especially for rough walls [4], irregular wall surface causes more intense particle-wall and particle-particle interactions. In the oil industry, hydraulic fracturing treatment has been widely used to develop tight gas and tight formations. During the treatment, high pressurized liquid is first injected to a well to initiate and propagate a fracture, and then particle-fluid porppant mixture is injected into the fracture. The injected proppant particles are used to inhibit fracture closure, which can provide a high conductivity channel for oil and gas flow from a formation to a well [5, 6]. Since the productivity of a stimulated well mainly depends on proppant placement in a fracture, it is of significant importance to predict proppant transport in a fracture. However, frequent particle-fluid, particle-particle and particle-wall interactions cause extremely complicated particle hydrodynamic and mechanical behavior, and this causes the question of proppant transport in a fracture has remained, for the most part, unanswered [7].

Based on the nature of particle-particle interactions, particle-fluid flow can be classified into three categories [8]: collision-free flow, collision-dominated flow and contact-dominated flow. For dense collision-dominated flow of particles submerged in a viscous fluid, both particle and fluid motions and their interactions need to be accurately modeled to account for the effect of particle collisions [9]. Generally, there are mainly two numerical methods to model particle-fluid flow interactions, the Eulerian-Eulerian and Eulerian-Lagrangian methods. In the Eulerian-Eulerian method [10, 11], both particle and fluid phases are treated as interpenetrating continuum media in a computational cell, and they are coupled using an ensemble

averaged drag force term in each momentum equation. In contrast, in the Eulerian-Lagrangian approach [12-14], the fluid phase is treated as continuum media while the solid phase is treated as discrete particles, and the particle trajectories can be accurately calculated by Lagrangian method.

Three Eulerian-Lagrangian approaches are commonly used: DNS (Direct Numerical Simulation) [15, 16], MP-PIC (Multiphase-Particle in Cell) [17, 18] and CFD-DEM [19, 20]. Since the computational cost of DNS is high, it only can deal with a small number of particles. In comparison, although MP-PIC can be applied to solve large-scale engineering problems, the particles-particles interactions cannot be fully captured. Ultimately, the motion of individual particles can be directly calculated using CFD-DEM approach, and more details of collision and contact between solid phases are accurately captured using the soft-sphere model [21]. In the recent years, the CFD-DEM approach has been gradually applied to investigate proppant transport in a hydraulic fracture. Tomac and Gutierrez [9] introduced a new particle contact model coupled in DEM and investigated the micro-mechanical behavior of particles in a narrow channel. Blyton et al. [22] modeled the motion and placement of proppant particles in a fracture using a coupled CFD-DEM code. Zeng et al. [23] proposed a representative model for upscaling the CFD-DEM to solve proppant transport in a hydraulic fracture in engineering scale. Although proppant transport in a fracture has been partly studied using CFD-DEM approach, the micro-mechanical behavior of proppant particles in a fracture is still unclear. In addition, to the best of our knowledge, no work is conducted to investigate particle transport in a rough fracture. In this work, a coupled CFD-DEM approach is employed to model particle transport between two rough parallel plates to improve the understanding of particle hydrodynamic and mechanical behavior in a hydraulic fracture, and the retardation effect of rough fracture walls on particle transport is quantitatively represented.

2. Computational models

Because the CFD-DEM approach has been discussed in detail in our previous studies [24, 25], only a

brief summary of the model is presented here.

2.1 Discrete element method

In the DEM, individual particles constitute the solid phase, which has two types of motion: translational and rotational motions. Newton's and Euler's second laws of motion are used to determine the linear and angular motions of particles, respectively, while the force-displacement law is used to update the magnitudes and directions of contact force. The governing equations of translational and rotational motion for particle i are described by the following equations, respectively,

$$m_i \frac{d\mathbf{v}_i}{dt} = \sum_{j=1}^k \mathbf{f}_{ij}^{p-p} + \mathbf{f}_i^{p-f} + m_i \mathbf{g} \quad (1)$$

$$I_i \frac{d\omega_i}{dt} = \sum_{j=1}^k \left(\mathbf{M}_{ij}^t + \mathbf{M}_{ij}^r \right) \quad (2)$$

where m_i is the particle mass (in kg); \mathbf{v}_i is the linear velocity (in m/s); t is time (in s); k is the number of particles in interaction with the particle; \mathbf{f}_{ij}^{p-p} is the particles-particles or particles-walls contact force (in N); \mathbf{f}_i^{p-f} is the force exerted on the particle from the fluid surrounding the particle (in N); I_i is the moment of inertia (in kg·m/s); ω_i is the angular velocity (in rad/s); \mathbf{M}_{ij}^t is the tangential torque (in N·m); and \mathbf{M}_{ij}^r is the rolling friction torque (in N·m).

The soft-sphere model [21] is used, in which the particles are allowed to have small overlaps when they contact, and the mechanical forces of particles-particles and particles-walls are calculated based on the overlaps using a force-displacement law. The mechanical forces includes normal and shear components, which can be calculated using the following equation by taking the elastic and viscous effects into consideration,

$$\mathbf{f}_{ij}^{p-p} = \left(K^n \delta^n - 2\gamma^n \sqrt{m_i K^n} \dot{\delta}^n \right) \mathbf{v}_i^n + \left(K^s \delta^s - 2\gamma^s \sqrt{m_i K^s} \dot{\delta}^s \right) \mathbf{v}_i^s \quad (3)$$

where K^n is the normal stiffness of the contact (in N/m); K^s is the shear stiffness of the contact (in N/m); δ^n

is the normal contact overlap (in m); δ^s is the shear contact overlap (in m); γ^n is the critical normal damping ratio; γ^s is the critical shear damping ratio; v_i^n is the relative normal velocity at the contact (in m/s); v_i^s is the relative shear velocity at the contact (in m/s).

2.2 Fluid phase equations

For the fluid phase, local-volume-averaged Navier-Stokes equations are used, and the effect of solid phase on fluid flow is introduced in terms of volumetric porosity and coupling force. The linear momentum conservation and continuity equation for mass conservation are given respectively by:

$$\rho_f \frac{\partial \varepsilon \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + \rho_f \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla (\varepsilon \mathbf{u}) = -\varepsilon \nabla p + \mu \nabla^2 (\varepsilon \mathbf{u}) + \mathbf{f}_b \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial t} + \nabla (\varepsilon \mathbf{u}) = 0 \quad (5)$$

where ρ_f is the fluid density (in kg/m³); ε is the porosity; \mathbf{u} is the fluid velocity (in m/s); p is the fluid pressure (in Pa); μ is the fluid dynamic viscosity (in Pa·s); and \mathbf{f}_b is the particle body force per unit volume (in N).

2.3 Implementation of CFD-DEM coupling

For CFD-DEM modeling, the parameters that couple CFD and DEM are the fluid volume fraction, volumetric momentum exchange and fluid-particle interaction force. Because the spatial resolution of particle variables is much smaller than that of fluid properties, interphase coupling in CFD-DEM requires special attention [26]. The two-dimensional Particle Flow Code (PFC^{2D} in version 4.0) is used in this study. The schematic diagram [27] of CFD-DEM is shown in Fig. 1. At each computational time step, the forces that act on a particle are computed, and then particle motion is calculated based on the Lagrangian approach using the law of motion and superposition of all the relevant forces. The fluid motion in computational cells is updated by formulating fluid phase equations based on the Eulerian approach. Those coupling parameters are calculated based on the position and velocity of particles and fluid properties (pressure and velocity).

2.4 Validation

Simulation of spherical particles settling in an incompressible viscous fluid has been conducted, and particle motion during simulation is recorded. The simulation results are compared with the experimental data published by Mordant and Pinton [28] to validate the CFD-DEM approach. A characteristic velocity $V = \sqrt{gd}$ and characteristic time $\tau = \sqrt{d/g}$ [29] are defined, and then dimensionless velocity and time are defined as V_f/V and t/τ , respectively, where V_f is settling velocity and t is time. The time evolution of particle settling velocity is shown in Fig. 2. It is clear that the spheres quickly reach a final velocity after a short period of acceleration, and both the terminal velocity and its evolution with time show good agreement between the simulation results and experimental data.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Particle settling between two parallel smooth plates

For a single particle settling in bounded fluid media, the confining boundaries exert extra hydrodynamic retardation, which significantly reduces particle settling velocity [30, 31]. Many works have been carried out to investigate the problem in a cylindrical tube [30, 32, 33] and between two parallel plates [34-36], and a wall factor is commonly used to represent the hydrodynamic retardation effect. However, when multi-particle settle in finite fluid, inter-particle and particles-walls interaction can further affect particle hydrodynamic and mechanical behavior.

Figure 3 shows snapshots of multi-particles (with $d=0.5$ mm) settling between two smooth parallel plates with a width of $W=6$ mm. It is clear that the flow field significantly changes due to particle settlement, which causes downward or upward flow of fluid in the gap between solid phases. In the central region of the channel, settling particles exert drag forces on the fluid, which mainly flows downwards through the channel and hinders particles to settle. The central particles squeeze the nearby fluid to both sides, and then the fluid near

boundaries changes to upward flow. Compared with particles settling in infinite unbounded fluid, the upward-flow fluid exerts extra hydrodynamic retardation on settling particles and reduces particle settling velocity. As more particles enter the channel, the gap between solid phases decreases, the upward-flow velocity of fluid increases, and this causes more intense retardation effect on settling particles. Since the particle concentration is low in this case, the inter-particle hindering effect is slight at the beginning of settling. However, as particles settle along the channel, due to the frequent particle-fluid, particle-particle and particle-wall interactions, an unstable flow field forms. It is observed at the lower part of the channel in Fig. 3(c), a small number of particles tended to concentrate with each other.

As the particles settle, their average settling velocity increases and gradually approaches a stable value corresponding to terminal settling velocity. During simulations, a measuring region was set to obtain the average settling velocity, and a lower position of the flow channel was chosen to ensure that the particles reach a stable settling velocity before entering the measuring region. The variation of particle average settling velocity against elapse time in a thinning fluid (with $\mu=0.0005$ Pa·s) is shown in Fig. 4. During early settlement stage, because no particle enters the measuring region, the particle average settling velocity is zero. When particles start to enter the measuring region, the average settling velocity dramatically increases. At the beginning, only a small number of particles entering into the region, so the average settling velocity is high. However, as more and more particles enter the measuring region, the particle concentration in the measuring region increases, which causes more intense inter-particle hindering, so particle average settling velocity gradually decreases and finally reaches a stable value. In addition, it also can be observed that the hydrodynamic retardation effect of plate walls on settling particles decreases as the aperture between the two parallel plates increase, so particle average settling velocity increases.

In order to quantitatively represent the hydrodynamic retardation effect of planar wall on settling

particles, a wall factor was employed. For multi-particle settling between two parallel plates, the wall factor can be defined as the ratio of particle average settling velocity (V_{MS}) falling between two parallel plates to that ($V_{MS\infty}$) in infinite fluid, so the average settling velocity of particles falling in infinite fluid must be obtained first. For different width between two parallel plates, numerous simulations have been implemented for particles with different sizes settling in different fluids. The parameters used in the simulations are summarized in Table 1, and finally the average settling velocities were calculated. Fig. 5 shows the variation of particle average settling velocity against a size ratio (d/W) of particle diameter to the width between two parallel plates. It is clear that particle average settling velocity linearly decreases with the increase in the size ratio, so an extrapolation method can be used to obtain particle average settling velocity in infinite fluid by extrapolating the asymptotic size ratio to $d/W=0$.

The wall factor $V_{MS}/V_{MS\infty}$ is then calculated, which is a function of the size ratio and particle Reynolds number, so a dimensionless composite parameter of $d/(W \cdot Re)$ is used. The variation of the wall factor against the dimensionless composite parameter is shown in Fig. 6. The results show that when $d/(W \cdot Re)$ is small (≤ 0.001), the effect of wall hydrodynamic retardation is slight and can be ignored, which causes $V_{MS}/V_{MS\infty} \approx 1$. As the dimensionless composite parameter increases, the wall hydrodynamic retardation effect starts to work, and particle average settling velocity decreases. It also can be observed that when particles settling in different regimes, the wall hydrodynamic retardation effects show different exhibitions. For particles settling in low-viscous fluid, particle Reynolds number is high ($472.96 \leq Re \leq 1261.98$), frequent particle interactions govern the main particle movements, and its effect on particle settling velocity overshadows the wall hydrodynamic retardation. Therefore, the wall factor almost stays constant ($V_{MS}/V_{MS\infty} \approx 1$) for particle settling in low-viscous fluid. However, when fluid viscosity is high, the flow field between two parallel plates is stable, a settling region with low particle Reynolds number is obtained, so the effect of wall hydrodynamic retardation becomes

dominant and particle average settling velocity significantly decreases with the increase in the size ratio. A correlation is proposed to represent the relationship between wall factor and dimensionless composite parameter as shown in Eq. 6.

$$\frac{V_{MS}}{V_{MS\infty}} = e^{-25.372 \frac{d}{W Re}} \quad (6)$$

where V_{MS} is particle average settling velocity falling between two parallel smooth plates (in m/s); $V_{MS\infty}$ is particle average settling velocity in infinite fluid (in m/s); d is particle diameter (in m); W is the width between two parallel plates (in m); and Re is particle Reynolds number. The prediction results show good agreement with simulation data in the range of $19.64 \leq Re \leq 1261.98$, and the average relative error is only 1.88%.

3.2 Particle settling between two parallel rough plates

For particles settling between two parallel rough plates, the irregular wall surface causes more frequently interactions of particles-particles and particles-walls, which significantly affect particle transport. In order to quantitatively characterize the effect of wall roughness on particle settling, the wall irregularity must be represented first. Barton and Choubey [37] proposed the joint roughness coefficient (JRC) to represent rock fracture roughness in the form of an irregular zigzag line

$$JRC = \frac{\arctan(\tau/\sigma_n) - \varphi_b}{\log_{10}(JCS/\sigma_n)} \quad (7)$$

where τ is the peak shear strength (in MN/m²); σ_n is the effective normal stress (in MN/m²); φ_b is the basic friction angle (in °); and JCS is the joint wall compressive strength (in MN/m²).

In this work, the published data by Barton and Choubey [37] is used to generate rough planar walls, and series of segments of straight lines were used to form the DEM walls. Then, particle settling between two parallel rough plates is simulated. Snapshots of the simulation results are shown in Fig. 7. It is clear that wall roughness promotes contact frequency inter-particles and between particles and walls, and this causes more

complex particle motion. Vortex also forms, which significantly changes particle transport direction, and particles are dragged to the center of the channel and inclined to agglomerate.

In order to represent wall roughness effect on particle settling, a dimensionless parameter V_{MR}/V_{MS} is presented, which is defined as roughness wall factor representing the ratio of particle average settling velocity (V_{MR}) between two parallel rough plates to that (V_{MS}) between two parallel smooth plates. The settling of multi-particle between two parallel rough plates was simulated, and the used parameters were summarized in Table 1. The roughness wall factor was calculated based on measured particle average settling velocity and. Fig. 8 shows the variation of roughness wall factor as a function of JRC. It is observed that when particles settle in high-viscous fluid, the flow field is relatively stable, and the interaction frequency between particles and walls increases with the increase in JRC. This causes particles to be inclined to move to a stable position (channel center), so most of the particles concentrate near the channel center. Since the upward-flow fluid velocity near the channel center is smaller than that of fluid near the walls, the fluid drag force on particles near the channel center is weaker, causing a higher particle settling velocity. As can be seen in Fig 8(a), particle average settling velocity linearly increases with increase in JRC. In contrast, for particles settling in low-viscous fluid, particle average settling velocity decreases with increases in JRC at high JRC, as shown in Fig 8(b). Because the flow field for low-viscous fluid is relatively unstable, particles interact more frequently with each other and walls. Therefore, particle lateral transport strengthens due to the frequent interaction for high JRC (≥ 10), which causes particles to form dispersive distribution in the channel. Thus, the mechanical interaction-induced retardation starts to work, so particle average settling velocity decreases.

According to the analyses in Section 3.1, it can be expected that when particles settle between two parallel rough plates, particle average settling velocity depends on parallel plate aperture, particle Reynold number and wall roughness. Accordingly, a dimensionless composite parameter $JRC(d/W)Re^{0.045}$ was

proposed, and the variation of roughness wall factor as a function of the composite parameters is shown in Fig. 9. It is clear that roughness wall factor first increases with the increase in the composite parameter and then decreases. For $JRC(d/W)Re^{0.045} \leq 3.5$, since particles mainly concentrate near channel center, the average settling velocity is higher than that for two smooth parallel plates, and the roughness wall factor is greater than 1. However, as the composite parameter further increases, the mechanical interaction-induced retardation effect starts to work and gradually changes to be dominant. Particle average settling velocity significantly decreases because of the particle-particle and particle-wall collisions. A correlation was established to represent the relationship between roughness wall factor and the composite parameter as given below

$$\frac{V_{MR}}{V_{MS}} = 1 - 0.0356 \times \left(JRC \times \frac{d}{W} \times Re^{0.045} \right)^2 + 0.1292 \times JRC \times \frac{d}{W} \times Re^{0.045} \quad (8)$$

where V_{MR} is the particle average settling velocity in finite fluid falling between two parallel rough plates (in m/s). It is clear that the correlation can accurately represent the relationship at the region of $25.04 \leq Re \leq 1456.59$.

Ultimately, for a single particle settling in finite fluid, the confined wall only exerts extra hydrodynamic retardation on settling particle. However, when multi-particle settle between two parallel plates, the mechanical interaction-induced frequent collisions of inter-particles and particles-walls significantly hinder particle settlement. Therefore, the extra wall retardation effect is constituted of hydrodynamic and mechanical retardations for multi-particle settling confined in finite fluid. Moreover, the mechanical retardation is significantly dependent on particle settling regimes and increases with the increase in particle Reynolds number.

3.3 Particle horizontal transport between two parallel smooth plates

For a still particle in a flowing fluid, the fluid exerts drag force on the particle, thus the particle is

accelerated and starts to move. Since the drag force is a function of the velocity discrepancy between fluid and particle, particle acceleration velocity gradually decreases while its transport velocity gradually approaches a stable value. However, due to energy dissipation, particles cannot transport as fast as the local fluid, and a velocity discrepancy between fluid and particle occurs, which is called slippage velocity. Because fluid drag force on a particle depends on particle and fluid properties, slippage velocity is a function of particle diameter and fluid viscosity. In addition, when particle-fluid mixture horizontally transports between two parallel plates, the channel's non-slip boundaries cause shear-induced particle longitudinal transport [38], so particles frequently interact with nearby particles and walls, and this affecting horizontal transport. Fig. 10 shows snapshots of particle horizontal transport between two smooth parallel plates. Clearly, the longitudinal velocity distribution of fluid is parabolic in shape, and the flow velocity along centerline is largest causing local particles to transport fastest, while the flow velocity near wall is smallest due to non-slip boundaries on upper and lower boundaries. According to Newton's law of internal friction, fluid shear force is proportion to longitudinal velocity gradient. Therefore, the fluid shear force exerting on particles near walls is maximum, and the particles are inclined to transport from high-shear region (near walls) to low-shear region (near the channel center) [38]. It is also observed that particles concentrate near channel center at the mixture front at a particle Reynold number of $Re=6.34$, which is analogous to fingering phenomenon. However, due to significantly longitudinal transport of particles, the shear-induced migration does not predict maximum concentration at channel center for high particle Reynolds number.

As particles are horizontally transported deep into the channel, the transport velocities of particle and fluid gradually become stable, and an equilibrium particle average transport velocity can be reached. A measuring region was set at the middle segment of the flow channel to eliminate the effects of inlet and outlet. Particle average transport velocity in the measuring region was determined, and its variation against elapse

time is shown in Fig. 11. During early stage of particle injection, because no particle enters the measuring region, the measured average transport velocity is zero. When the leading particles enter this section, the average transport velocity dramatically increases. However, because only a small number of particles, which mainly occupy the position near channel center, enter the measuring region during this stage, the average transport velocity is high. As more and more particles become present in the measuring region, interactions of particles-particles and particles-walls increase and this significantly affects particle transport. Thus, particle average transport velocity decreases and gradually comes to be a terminal equilibrium value when particle volumetric concentration in the measuring region becomes stable. Moreover, because particles occupy part of the space of flow channel, the flow velocity of interstitial fluid is higher than the injection velocity according to the conservation law of fluid mass. Furthermore, the high velocity fluid exerts a large drag force on particles causing a high particle average transport velocity.

It also can be observed from Fig. 11 that parallel plate walls hinder particle horizontal transport. The average transport velocity decreases with the decrease in the aperture between the two parallel plates. Since it is difficult to obtain fluid flow velocity nearby particles, the injection velocity is used to calculate the slippage velocity between particles and fluid, which indicates the difference of particle average transport velocity to injection velocity. A characteristic velocity $V = \sqrt{gd}$ [29] is used to normalize the slippage velocity. Fig. 12 shows the variation of dimensionless slippage velocity against a size ratio of d/W . It is clear that as the aperture between the two parallel plates decreases, the size ratio of d/W increases, so the retardation effect of plate walls on particle transport enhances, which causes particle average transport velocity and slippage velocity to decrease.

Obviously, the slippage velocity is a function of the size ratio and injection velocity. Moreover, as mentioned above in Section 3.2, particles exhibit different hydrodynamic behavior under different particle

transport regimes and the slippage velocity is also dependent on particle Reynolds number. In order to determine the slippage velocity, two dimensionless composite parameters were proposed, $\sqrt{C_D \text{Re}^2} / (d/W)$ and $\text{Re}(V_{inj} / \sqrt{gd})^{0.105}$. The first parameter is only dependent on particle diameter, while the second parameter is a function of slippage velocity. Both the drag coefficient and particle Reynolds number were calculated from slippage velocity. According to the simulation results under different parameters summarized in Table 1, the two dimensionless composite parameters were calculated and their relationship is shown in Fig. 13. Clearly, $\sqrt{C_D \text{Re}^2} / (d/W)$ increases linearly against $\text{Re}(V_{inj} / \sqrt{gd})^{0.105}$ in a log-log scale, and a power-law correlation was used to fit the simulation results as shown in Eq. (9). Generally, the correlation can be directly used to determine the average transport velocity for multi-particle horizontally transport between two parallel smooth plates.

$$\sqrt{C_D \text{Re}^2} / \frac{d}{W} = 55 \text{Re}^{0.8776} \left(\frac{V_{inj}}{\sqrt{gd}} \right)^{0.0921} \quad (9)$$

where V_{inj} is the injection velocity (in m/s).

3.4 Particle horizontal transport between two parallel rough plates

As analyzed in Section 3.2, rough plate walls can enhance particle interactions with each other and with walls, and this causes strong mechanical retardation on settling particles. Therefore, as can be expected when particles horizontally transport between two parallel rough plates, their hydrodynamic and mechanical behavior can be significantly affected. Fig. 14 shows snapshots of particle horizontally transport between two parallel rough plates. Compared with smooth plates, particles more frequently interact with each other and walls due to the mechanical retardation effect of rough plate walls and this causes particles to transport away from horizontal direction. A measuring region was set at middle part of the flow channel, particle average longitudinal transport velocity was measured and its variation against elapse time is shown in Fig. 15. Observably, for particles transport between two parallel smooth plates with JRC=0, particles horizontal

transport is dominant, and the effect of particles-particles and particles-walls interactions on horizontal transport is ignored. However, when particles horizontally transport between two parallel rough plates, the frequent interactions causes a large longitudinal transport velocity.

For dramatically frequent interactions of particles-particles and particles-walls, particle longitudinal transport can significantly hinder its horizontal transport, so some particles start to concentrate and agglomerate. This further hinders the horizontal transport of following particles and causes more severe agglomeration, and finally even blocks the flow channel. Fig. 16 shows particle agglomeration snapshots transporting between two parallel rough plates. It is clear that particle agglomeration in the channel causes severe blockage, which prohibits following injected particles from further horizontal transport. It is also observed that particles tightly squeeze with each other and large contact force, which is marked by red line, is obtained at the contact positions of particles-particles and particles-walls. In addition, as the injection velocity increases, the instability of flow field in the channel strengthens and this causes more frequent solid-solid interactions, leading to more severe agglomeration and blockage.

In this section, the effect of plate roughness on particle horizontal transport is quantitatively investigated. The rough wall-induced mechanical retardation effect is represented by rough wall factor (V_{MTR}/V_{MTS}), which represents the ratio of particle average horizontal transport velocity (V_{MTR}) between two parallel rough plates to that (V_{MTS}) in two parallel smooth plates. Similarly, simulations for multi-particle horizontally transport between two parallel rough plates under different parameters were implemented. The variation of the rough wall factor against JRC was first investigated as shown in Fig. 17. Compared with smooth plate walls, particles more frequently interact with each other and walls when they are confined between two rough plate walls, and strong mechanical interactions reduce particle horizontal transport velocity, causing the value of V_{MTR}/V_{MTS} to be less than 1. It is clear from Figs. 17(a) and (b) that the rough wall factor decreases with the

increase in JCR. However, when particles are driven by high-viscous fluid, the mechanical interaction-induced retardation has little effect on particle horizontal transport, which causes to become $V_{MTR}/V_{MTR} \approx 1$ and can be ignored as shown in Figs. 17(c) and 17(d). Generally, the mechanical interaction-induced retardation is dependent on particle transport regimes as mentioned above. For low-viscous fluid, particle Reynold number is large ($10.91 \leq Re \leq 148.78$), the mechanical interaction-induced retardation is dominant, while the mechanical interaction-induced retardation is ignored for high-viscous fluid with small particle Reynold number ($4.08 \leq Re \leq 17.15$).

Since particles exhibit different behavior in different transport regimes, in order to quantitatively characterize the retardation effect induced by mechanical interaction, the transport regions must be divided first. A dimensionless composite parameter of Ar/Re was presented, and Ar is the Archimedes number, which denotes the ratio of buoyancy force to inertia force. The variation of rough wall factor against Ar/Re is shown in Fig. 18. For small Ar/Re (≤ 11.15), the rough wall factor is almost independent of Ar/Re while it dramatically decreases with the increase in Ar/Re when it exceeds 11.15. When particles are driven by high-viscous fluids, the flow field in the channel is stable, so mechanical interaction-induced retardation is small and can be ignored. However, for low-viscous fluids, the interactions of particles-particles and particles-walls dramatically increase, mechanical interaction-induced retardation starts to work and gradually changes to be dominant, so particle horizontal transport velocity significantly decreases.

For $Ar/Re \leq 11.15$, rough wall factor almost keeps constant, it just is a function of JRC, size ratio and injection velocity, so a dimensionless composite parameter of $JRC(d/W)(V_{inj}/\sqrt{gd})$ was proposed. The variation of rough wall factor against the composite parameter is shown in Fig. 19. A good linear relationship between rough wall factor and the composite parameter is obtained. The following linear function is used to represent the relationship as shown in Eq. (10), and good agreement is obtained.

$$\frac{V_{MTR}}{V_{MTR}} = 1 - 0.0066 \text{JRC} \frac{d}{W} \frac{V_{inj}}{\sqrt{gd}} \quad 0.78 \leq \frac{\text{Ar}}{\text{Re}} \leq 11.15 \quad (10)$$

where V_{MTR} is particle average horizontal transport velocity between two parallel rough plates (in m/s); V_{MTR} is particle average horizontal transport velocity between two parallel smooth plates (in m/s); V_{inj} is particle injection velocity (in m/s); and Ar is particle Archimedes number.

In contrast, the instability of flow field between two parallel rough plates increases at high Ar/Re region, which causes more frequent inter-particle and particle-wall interactions. The mechanical interaction-induced retardation gradually governs particle transport, so rough wall factor is also a function of particle Reynolds number. A new dimensionless composite parameter $(\text{Re}/\text{JRC} \cdot \text{Ar})(W/d)(\sqrt{gd}/V_{inj})$ was proposed, and the variation of rough wall factor against the composite parameter is shown in Fig. 20. As can be seen, the rough wall factor dramatically increases with the increase in the composite parameter, and gradually approaches an equilibrium value of $V_{MTR}/V_{MTR}=1$. A new correlation, Eq. (11), was established to represent the relationship between rough wall factor and the composite parameter at high Ar/Re region, which shows good prediction capability.

$$\frac{V_{MTR}}{V_{MTR}} = 1 - \frac{\text{JRC} \frac{d}{W} \frac{V_{inj}}{\sqrt{gd}}}{\text{JRC} \frac{d}{W} \frac{V_{inj}}{\sqrt{gd}} + 238.56 \frac{\text{Re}}{\text{Ar}}} \quad 11.15 < \frac{\text{Ar}}{\text{Re}} \leq 394.92 \quad (11)$$

4. Conclusions

The settlement and horizontal transport of multi-particle between two parallel plates were simulated using a coupled CFD-DEM approach, and the hydrodynamic and mechanical retardation effects on migration particles were quantitatively investigated. For multi-particle settling between two parallel plates, plate walls exert strong hydrodynamic retardation on settling particles and reduce their settling velocities. In contrast, particles frequently interact with each other and walls when confined between two parallel rough plates, and

the mechanical interaction exerts extra retardation and further decreases particle settling velocity. When multi-particle horizontally transports between two parallel plates, particles tend to migrate from high-shear region (near plate walls) to low-shear region (channel center). This causes particle horizontal transport velocity to increase, which is even larger than the injection velocity. Plate walls also exert strong hydrodynamic retardation on particle horizontal transport, and the slippage velocity significantly decreases with the increase in the ratio of particle diameter to the aperture between two parallel plates. In addition, the mechanical interaction of particles-particles and particles-walls significantly strengthens when particles are confined between two parallel rough plates. This increases particle longitudinal transport and hinders its horizontal transport, and particles even agglomerate with each other and clog the channel. Generally, the hydrodynamic retardation is dominant for low particle Reynolds number. On the contrary, particles more frequently interact with each other and walls at high particle Reynolds number regime, causing the mechanical interaction-induced retardation to start to work and gradually to govern particle transport.

Conflict of interest

The authors declared that there is no conflict of interest.

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Nomenclature

Symbols

Ar particle Archimedes number

C_d drag coefficient

d	particle diameter (m)
f_i^{p-f}	force exerted on the particle from the fluid surrounding the particle (N)
f_{ij}^{p-p}	particle-particle or particle-wall contact force (N)
f_b	particle body force per unit volume (N)
JCS	joint wall compressive strength (MN/m ²)
JRC	joint roughness coefficient
i	particle index
I_i	inertia moment (kg·m/s)
k	the number of particles in interaction with the particle
K_n	normal stiffness at the contact (N/s)
K_s	shear stiffness at the contact (N/m)
m_i	particle mass (kg)
M_{ij}^r	particle rolling friction torque (N·m)
M_{ij}^t	particle tangential torque (N·m)
p	fluid pressure (Pa)
Re	particle Reynolds number
t	time (s)
u	fluid velocity (m/s)
v_i	particle linear velocity (m/s)
v_n	relative normal velocity at the contact (m/s)
v_s	relative shear velocity at the contact (m/s)
V	characteristic velocity (m/s)

V_{inj}	injection velocity (m/s)
V_{MR}	average settling velocity for particles falling between two parallel rough plates (m/s)
V_{MS}	average settling velocity for particles falling between two parallel smooth plates (m/s)
$V_{MS\infty}$	particle average settling velocity in infinite fluid (m/s)
V_p	particle average horizontal transport velocity (m/s)
V_{MTR}	particle average horizontal transport velocity between two parallel rough plates (m/s)
V_{MTS}	particle average horizontal transport velocity between two parallel smooth plates (m/s)
V_y	particle average lateral transport velocity (m/s)
W	width or aperture between two parallel plates (m)

Greek Symbols

γ_n	critical normal damping ratio
γ_s	critical shear damping ratio
δ_n	normal contact overlap (m)
δ_s	shear contact overlap (m)
ε	porosity
μ	fluid dynamic viscosity (Pa·s)
ρ_f	fluid density (kg/m ³)
σ_n	effective normal stress (MN/m ²)
τ	peak shear strength (MN/m ²)
φ_b	basic friction angle (°)
ω	particle angular velocity (rad/s)

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Table 1. Range of simulation parameters used.

Simulation	Plate	d / mm	W / mm	μ / Pa·s	V_{inj} / m/s	JRC
Settling	Smooth		2, 4, 6, 8, 10	0.0001, 0.0005,	-	-
	Rough	0.35, 0.5,	4, 6, 8	0.001	-	5, 10, 20
Horizontal transport	Smooth	0.65	2, 4, 6, 8, 10	0.001, 0.005,	0.1,	-
	Rough		4, 6, 8	0.01	0.15, 0.2	5, 10, 20

Fig. 1. CFD and DEM coupling scheme [27].

Fig. 2. The temporal evolution of the settling velocity of a sphere falling in water. The solid lines refer to the experimental data of Mordant and Pinton [28], and the dashed lines indicate simulation results.

Fig. 3. Snapshots of particle settling between two smooth parallel plates with a width of 6 mm.

Fig. 4. Variation of average settling velocity against elapse time for particles settling between two smooth parallel plates ($d=0.5\text{mm}$, $\mu=0.0005 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$).

Fig. 5. Variation of particle average settling velocity against particle size to parallel plate aperture ratio

($\mu=0.001 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$).

Fig. 6. Wall hydrodynamic retardation on multi-particles settling between two parallel smooth plates.

(a) JRC=5

(b) JRC=10

(c) JRC=20

Fig. 7. Snapshot of particles settling between two rough parallel rough plates with a width of 6 mm and different wall roughnesses.

(a) $\mu=0.001 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$

(b) $\mu=0.0001 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$

Fig. 8. Variation of rough wall factor as a function of JRC for particles falling between two rough parallel plates.

Fig. 9. Variation of rough wall factor against the composite parameter for particles falling between two rough parallel plates.

Fig. 10. Snapshots of particle horizontal transport between two smooth parallel plates with a width of 6 mm.

Fig. 11. Variation of particle average horizontal transport velocity against elapse time for flow between two rough parallel plates ($d=0.5\text{mm}$, $\mu=0.001\text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$, $V_{inj}=0.2\text{m/s}$).

Fig. 12. Variation of dimensionless slippage velocity against size ratio for particle horizontal transport between two smooth parallel plates.

Fig. 13. Variation of $\sqrt{C_D \text{Re}^2} / (d/W)$ against $\text{Re}\left(\frac{V_{inj}}{\sqrt{gd}}\right)^{0.105}$ for particle horizontal transport between two parallel smooth plates.

(a) JRC=5

(b) JRC=10

(c) JRC=20

Fig. 14. Snapshots of particle horizontal transport between two rough parallel plates with a width of 6 mm and different wall roughnesses.

Fig. 15. Particle average longitudinal transport velocity between two parallel rough plates.

(a) $V_{inj}=0.1$ m/s

(b) $V_{inj}=0.2$ m/s

Fig. 16. Snapshots of particle agglomeration between two rough parallel plates.

(a) $\mu=0.001 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}, W=4 \text{ mm}$

(b) $\mu=0.001 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}, W=8 \text{ mm}$

(c) $\mu=0.01 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}, W=4 \text{ mm}$

(d) $\mu=0.01 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}, W=8 \text{ mm}$

Fig. 17. Variation of particle average horizontal transport velocity ratio as a function of JRC for flow between two rough parallel plates.

Fig. 18. Variation of particle average horizontal transport velocity ratio against the composite Ar/Re

parameter for particle transport between two rough parallel plates.

Fig. 19. Variation of particle average horizontal transport velocity ratio against $JRC \frac{d}{W} \frac{V_{inj}}{\sqrt{gd}}$ at low Ar/Re

region.

Fig. 20. Variation of particle average horizontal transport velocity ratio against $\frac{Re}{JRC \cdot Ar} \cdot \frac{W}{d} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{gd}}{V_{inj}}$ at high

Ar/Re region.